

Captive care and reproduction of the common snapping turtle, *Chelydra s. serpentina*

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INTRODUCTION

The common snapping turtle (*Chelydra serpentina*) is a species that is rarely kept in captivity. The most likely reason is that the adults reach a size (up to 47 cm) that is too large to maintain in a regular aquarium. In addition, their aggressive behaviour does not endear them to turtle hobbyists. On that note, even though a bite by an adult snapping turtle appears to be painful, it rarely causes lacerations (ERNST et al., 1998). A direct consequence of this lack of popularity is that these animals are rarely bred in captivity. Only LEHMANN (1966) and the Iguana Reptile Zoo in Vlissingen, The Netherlands, (NETTEN & ZUURMOND, 1985) have reported on their captive husbandry.

SYSTEMATICS AND DISTRIBUTION

The family Chelydridae is assigned to the suborder Cryptodira and the order Chelonii (Testudines) and contains the genera *Chelydra* and *Macrolemys*. Both are large freshwater turtles with a characteristic massive head and powerful jaws.

The exact systematic arrangement of *Chelydra serpentina* is still subject to debate. According to ERNST & BARBOUR (1989) and ERNST et al. (1994) the species contains a nominate subspecies and three additional subspecies: *Chelydra serpentina osceola*, *Chelydra serpentina rossignonii*, and *Chelydra serpentina acutirostris*.

Juvenile *Chelydra serpentina*, the Snapping turtle.

Photo: P. Staljanssens

However, in a more recent publication (ERNST et al., 1998) the authors split up the genus *Chelydra* into three species. *Chelydra serpentina* comprises the nominate form (*Chelydra s. serpentina*) whose distribution range roughly extends from southern Canada through the eastern part of the USA to the coast of Texas. The subspecies *Chelydra s. osceola* is only found in Florida. *Chelydra rossignonii* inhabits a large part of Central America, whereas *Chelydra acutirostris* is found in

parts of Honduras, Colombia, Ecuador, and the Caribbean.

The natural habitat of snapping turtles comprises shallow, slowly moving rivers with aquatic vegetation, a soft bottom, and sufficient hiding places (ERNST et al., 1998).

CARE OF THE ANIMALS

For the last ten years, a male (carapace length: 210 mm; weight: 2,800 g) and two females (carapace length: 240 mm and 230 mm; weight: 4,000 g and 3,600 g) have been maintained in an aquarium of 200x50x60 cm (lxwxh). The temperature of the thirty-centimetre deep water fluctuates around 20°C most of the year, but the animals are put through an annual hibernation period of three months. During this period, the temperature goes down to 5-10°C and the animals are not fed. The aquarium, which includes several hiding places, does not receive any direct sunlight. Outside of the mating season, the male is separated from the females by a vertical screen. There is no land section.

An adult Snapping Turtle, *Chelydra serpentina*.

Photo: J. Hofstra

In nature snapping turtles rarely leave the water, though HAAS (1985) reports that his animals, which were kept in an outdoor enclosure, frequently left the pond to bask. However, on hot days the animals would invariably be found in the water. He suspected that they did this to avoid rapid dehydration. It is interesting to note that STONE & IVERSON (1999) concluded from experiments that in freshwater turtles that display little terrestrial activity, such as *Chelydra serpentina* and *Apalone spinifera*, the relation between skin surface and body weight is higher than in species that occasionally leave the water to bask, such as *Sternotherus odoratus*, *Kinosternon subrubrum*, and *Trachemys scripta*. Therefore, the rate of evaporation and chance of dehydration when exposed to high air temperatures outside of the water is probably higher in the former two species.

Even though snapping turtles are omnivores in nature (ERNST et al., 1998) these captive raised adults are only fed fish, shrimp, and cow heart. Jelle Hofstra (Gorredijk, The Netherlands) has a *Chelydra serpentina* which in the over thirty years it inhabited its terrarium has never eaten any vegetable matter (Hofstra, pers. comm.).

MATING BEHAVIOUR

Males of this species are sexually mature at an age of four to five years and a carapace length of 120-140 mm (LEHMANN, 1966; ERNST et al., 1998). Females, on the other hand, do not reach sexual maturity in the northern part of their range until 11-13 years of age, and on average produce their first clutch of eggs after 17-19 years (ERNST et al., 1998). At this point in their life they have a carapace length of around twenty centimetres.

In nature, these animals mate between April and November (CARR, 1952; ERNST et al., 1998). Every year our male is placed with the females during the month of July. Since they often bite each other, the period of contact is purposely kept short so as not to expose the animals to too much stress.

It is noteworthy that the male seems to prefer the smaller and less aggressive female. Possibly this has something to do with the fact that the larger female is very aggressive when the male approaches her.

Mating occurred almost on a daily basis and usually followed the same pattern. The male would follow the female around and eventually mount her. Sometimes he would stand in front of her with his hind limbs stretched and the posterior part of the carapace held high. Since this posture did not stimulate the female very much, he proceeded to follow the female around again shortly after.

When mating, the male holds on to the carapace of the female with his claws while curving his tail underneath the female's tail. Next, he introduces his penis inside the female's cloaca. Meanwhile, the female is bitten in the head or the skin of the neck. Usually, the female tries to shake the male by rapidly rotating her body.

A mating ritual such as the one described by LEGLER (1955; cit. ERNST et al., 1998) was not observed. LEGLER (1955) noted that both sexes approached one another until their noses were only two centimetres apart. The plastron was touching the ground in the front, whereas the posterior part was elevated with the hind limbs stretched out completely. The animals suddenly displayed simultaneous sideways movements with their head and neck. After that they slowly returned their heads into the forward position. This display was repeated ten times with an intermediate pause of about ten seconds. Just like in our animals, he observed matings where the male immediately mounted the females. TAYLOR (1933; cit. ERNST et al., 1998) described two snapping turtles that were located in shallow water with their heads turned toward each other. The animals were sucking up water and blowing it out above the water surface through their nostrils; he considered this behaviour to be a courtship display.

LAYING EGGS

Clutch 2000

Near the middle of February, roughly one month after the end of hibernation, the smaller female stopped eating. By probing the groin area, eggs could be felt. An X-ray photograph taken at a later date revealed twenty-four eggs.

In an attempt to have the turtle deposit her eggs under natural circumstances, she was placed in a terrarium (0.5 m²) at an air temperature of 22°C and containing a 15 cm deep layer of sand. Some attempts to excavate a nest cavity were made, but she did not deposit any eggs. Subsequently, the female was transferred to a large 12 m² area with several potential nesting sites. Since this did not result in any clutches after three days, we decided to chemically induce the egg laying by giving her an intraperitoneal injection of oxytocin (6-8 I.U.) and calciumgluconate (50-100 mg calcium per kg body weight). We injected different combinations of these chemicals on six occasions over the course of two months (see table 1), with varying results. After each injection the female made attempts to excavate a nest cavity, but this did not always result in deposition of eggs. The final fourteen eggs were actually laid without a preceding injection. The number of eggs deposited varied from one to nine. One egg broke during oviposition.

An X-ray shows the eggs inside the female *Chelydra serpentina*.

Photo: P. Staljanssens

Date	Injections	Result
18/02/2000	100 mg calcium/kg	Attempts to excavate nest cavity
21/02/2000	50 mg calcium/kg 6 I.U. oxytocine	Attempts to excavate nest cavity
24/02/2000	50 mg calcium/kg 6 I.U. oxytocine	Attempts to excavate nest cavity
28/02/2000	50 mg calcium/kg 6 I.U. oxytocine	Attempts to excavate nest cavity
20/03/2000	50 mg calcium/kg 8 I.U. oxytocine	Attempts to excavate nest cavity 1 egg (broken)
07/04/2000	50 mg calcium/kg 8 I.U. oxytocine	Attempts to excavate nest cavity
18/04/2000	50 mg calcium/kg 10 I.U. oxytocine	Attempts to excavate nest cavity 8 eggs
19/04/2000		1 egg
25/04/2000		1 egg
26/04/2000		1 egg
28/04/2000		1 egg
02/05/2000		Attempts to excavate nest cavity 9 eggs
10/05/2000		1 egg
11/05/2000		1 egg

Table 1. Data and results on the chemically induced oviposition of the female *Chelydra s. serpentina*

(kg = kilogram body weight).

Eggs of *Chelydra s. serpentina* are spherical and hard-shelled immediately after oviposition. To avoid bursting of the eggs because of an excessive uptake of water, we opted for a 'not too moist' vermiculite substrate for incubation. The eggs were buried with about three-quarters of their length in the substrate and incubated at 26-28°C and maximum relative humidity. After several days one could observe a white spot in eleven of the eggs, indicating that they were fertilised. After ten days, it was possible to see a premature embryo inside the egg when held up to the light. Unfertilised eggs maintained their yellowish-orange colour.

Upon checking the eggs three weeks into the incubation, six eggs were dented, most likely because the substrate was too

dry. After adding more water, only one egg recovered. The remaining five were dead. Apparently, snapping turtle eggs require relatively high substrate water content. A sixth (not dented) egg died after four weeks. The remaining five embryos appeared to develop well. After 77 days, three young cut through the eggshell with their egg tooth, a fourth did the same thing after 84 days. The fifth egg contained a deformed, dead young. Three hatchlings still had a yolk residue of about one centimetre in diameter upon hatching. One baby turtle completely absorbed the remainder of the yolk within four days. The other two never managed to absorb their yolk residues and died after three weeks, probably due to a yolk residue infection. The fourth remaining juvenile had already absorbed all yolk upon hatching.

Clutches 2001

On March 10, the smaller female spontaneously deposited a clutch of eggs in a sand-filled container. The 34 eggs were buried at a depth of 20-25 cm. Because of the relatively unsatisfying result of the previous clutch we decided to divide up the eggs and have both authors involved in the incubation. At the same time we decided to attempt different moisture levels for the substrate. In order to accomplish this we added 150, 170, 180, 200, 215, 230 and 250 grams of tap water respectively to 50 grams of vermiculite. Per substrate moisture level four eggs are incubated, except for the 200 gram water substrate which

contained 10 eggs. Six eggs of the latter ten, and the four eggs of the 180 gram water substrate were transported over 50 km by car to the home of the second author.

Ratio vermiculite/water	50/150	50/170	50/180	50/200	50/200	50/215	50/230	50/250
Number of eggs incubated	4	4	4	4	6	4	4	4
Number of eggs fertilised	3	3	4	4	3	3	4	3
Number of fertilised eggs hatched	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	3
% fertilised eggs hatched	100	100	75	50	67	67	50	100

Table 2. Results of the incubation of the first clutch of 2001 (**incubated by the second author**).

All eggs were incubated at 28-30°C. It is remarkable that the eggshell becomes flexible after two to three weeks of incubation. This was not noted during the 2000 incubation. The diameter of the recently deposited eggs varied between 25.5-34 mm at a weight of 12-15 g. ERNST et al. (1994) indicated values that fluctuated between 23-33 mm and 5-15 gram. During incubation the eggs swell through absorption of water.

With the first author, four eggs out of 24 were unfertilised, five embryos died during incubation and fifteen young opened the eggshell after 72-82 days (see table 2). With the second author, three out of ten eggs were unfertilised, two embryos died inside the egg, and five young hatched after 78-81 days (table 2).

Even though no mating was observed, the larger female also deposited a clutch. All 36 eggs were significantly smaller (24.5-26.5 mm) than those of the smaller female and turned out to be unfertilised after incubation.

Clutch of *Chelydra serpentina*.

Photo: P. Staljanssens

THE YOUNG

The carapace of young *Chelydra s. serpentina* is black with three keels that become less pronounced with age or when the turtles grow rapidly. The plastron is dark with some lighter specks. The strikingly long tail approaches the carapace in length.

After resorbing the yolk residue, the young had a carapace length of 26-36 mm at an average weight of 11 gram (n=5) which is considerably heavier than the 5-9 grams reported by ERNST et al. (1994).

The juveniles were placed in small rearing containers with shards of flowerpots for cover. The water temperature fluctuated over the months and between the two authors within a range of 13 to 24°C. Since snapping turtles are not great swimmers, the water level was kept such that their head was above the water when they extended their neck upwards.

Within a few days the juveniles started accepting food, which consisted of mosquito larvae, pieces of fish, earthworms, cow heart, and cat food. On this diet the young grew explosively. After six months, the two remaining juveniles from the first clutch had a carapace length of 7 and 8 centimetres at a weight of 100 and 188 grams.

Raising these aggressive animals together with other species is not recommended. For example, a juvenile *Trachemys scripta elegans* was bitten to death.

DISCUSSION

Many questions remain unanswered after our experience with breeding snapping turtles. For example, the fact that the eggs we incubated had a hard shell. Other authors have described the eggshell as "tough" (ERNST & BARBOUR, 1989; ERNST et al., 1998), "pliable shelled", (PACKARD et al., 1980) or "flexible-shelled" (PACKARD & DEMARCO, 1991). This apparent inconsistency is probably explained by the fact that the eggshell loses its rigidity about one to two weeks into incubation. LEHMANN (1966) also reports that his eggs were initially hard-shelled and only turned soft after three weeks, probably due to a lower incubation temperature (20-25°C). A similar phenomenon also appears to happen in *Chinemys reevesii* (Janssen, pers. comm.). We were not able to find any explanations in the literature for the softening of the shell.

Newly hatched *Chelydra serpentina*.

Photo: P. Staljanssens

The fact that in the year 2000 not all eggs were deposited at once could be due to stress. NETTEN & ZUURMOND (1985) also report that in Iguana Reptile Zoo the entire clutch was deposited over a time period of three weeks. However, depositing eggs over a prolonged time period does not seem normal to us. An injection of too low a dose of oxytocin may have been the reason for this behaviour. EWERT & LEGLER (1978) recommend 1 I.U. oxytocin per 100

gram body weight. LEHMANN (1966), on the other hand, injected only 1 I.U. oxytocin into a female weighing 2590 g and got good results.

It is striking that the eggs produced by the smaller female were larger and heavier than any report from the literature (LEHMANN, 1966; HOTALING et al., 1985; ERNST et al., 1998). A possible explanation could be that our animals, taking into consideration their carapace length, were considerably heavier than the individuals from nature, measured and weighed by LAGLER & APPLGATE (1943) (see graph).

Carapace length (CL) as a function of the body weight of *Chelydra serpentina* in nature and captivity.

FINKLER & CLAUSSEN (1997) found that larger eggs of *Chelydra serpentina* also contained more albumin and yolk, thus providing the hatchlings an advantage since they have access to more nutrients during their embryonic development.

On the other hand, PACKARD et al. (1980), PACKARD et al. (1982) and MILLER (1993) found out experimentally that a higher moisture level in the incubation substrate resulted in larger and heavier hatchlings, which in turn resulted in a higher survival rate since these young were more agile both on land and in the water (MILLER et al., 1987).

Our incubation periods are relatively long compared with the 63-70 days reported by YNTEMA (1978) for eggs incubated at 26-28°C. However, this may be explained by the fact

that the animals reported upon by this author originated from a more northerly population. EWERT (1985) discovered that eggs from such animals, incubated at a constant temperature, had a shorter incubation period than eggs from animals living in southern areas.

MILLER (1993) reported that the eggs of *Chelydra serpentina* incubated in a moist substrate (-150 kPa) had a incubation period that was on average four days shorter than the eggs that were incubated in a drier one (-850 kPa). During the 2001 incubation period, we were not able to track the influence of the substrate moisture level on the size of the hatchlings and the duration of the incubation since after hatching we were not able to identify the hatchlings individually. Of course, the number of eggs incubated was too small to draw any statistically relevant conclusions. From the results of the 2001 incubations (see table 2) we did realise that all of the different substrate moisture levels used during incubation gave

Juvenile *Chelydra serpentina*.

Photo: P. Staljanssens

good to excellent results. We think that it is better to incubate future clutches at the highest substrate moisture level, which is supported by the literature. We also do not preclude that an even higher substrate moisture level may be possible or even beneficial.

Transporting eggs shortly after oviposition does not necessary lead to the death of the embryo. This was shown for the first time with the eggs of the marine turtle *Caretta caretta* (HARRY & LIMPUS, 1989) which were first cooled to 7-10°C and then transported by car and aeroplane to a lab. These authors assumed that the transport of turtle eggs without sustaining a heightened mortality is possible due to the fact that the membranes surrounding the embryo are not attached to the inner egg membrane shortly after oviposition. Under natural conditions, this process takes place sixteen to eighteen hours after oviposition.

The relatively high percentages of unfertilised eggs (54% and 20% respectively) could be explained by the fact that the last copulations occurred seven months before the females were determined to be gravid. In Iguana Reptile Zoo in Vlissingen, the Netherlands (NETTEN & ZUURMOND, 1985), and with LEHMANN (1966) only half the clutch was fertilised after the same amount of time. In some reptiles, the male's sperm can be stored for a prolonged period of time after mating. In turtles this storage takes place in the mucous membrane in the upper part of the oviducts (GIST & JONES, 1989; RUDLOFF, 1990). However, the fertility of the sperm does decrease over time. For example, HILDEBRAND (1929; cit. PETZOLD, 1982) reports that in *Malaclemys centrata* nearly all eggs in a clutch were fertilised one year after mating. After four years this number had decreased to approximately four out of one hundred.

From data provided by GIST & JONES (1989) we can conclude that the maximum duration of the viability of stored sperm is most likely species specific.

As in most turtles the sex of juvenile *Chelydra serpentina* is determined by the incubation temperature (YNTEMA, 1976). However, the snapping turtle differs from other species of turtles that display this phenomenon in that there are three (instead of two) sex determining temperature levels. At 20°C only females are produced, at 23-24°C males, and above 29°C again only females. In nature, the average temperature in the centre of a nest fluctuates between 21-31°C (CONGDON & GIBBONS, 1990). We incubated the eggs at temperatures between 26-30°C so that most of the young will probably be females.

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SUMMARY

We succeeded in the captive breeding of *Chelydra serpentina* for two years in a row. A male and two females were maintained separately for most of the year. For one month out of the year the male was placed with the females where he would then mate repeatedly with the smaller female. A first clutch of twenty-four eggs was deposited over a period of approximately two months after repeated intraperitoneal injections with oxytocin (6-8 I.U.) and calcium gluconate (50-100 mg calcium per kilogram body weight). The eggs were incubated on moist vermiculite at a temperature of 26-28°C and 100% relative humidity. Eleven eggs turned out to be fertilised, but only four young hatched after 77-84 days. This poor result was most likely due to the substrate being too dry.

A second clutch of thirty-four eggs was deposited spontaneously in moist sand. Both authors incubated these eggs at 28-30°C, varying the level of substrate moisture over seven different values. In order to achieve this, ten eggs were transported fifty kilometres by car to the home of the second author shortly after they were deposited. Out of this clutch, twenty-seven eggs were fertilised. Twenty young hatched after 72-82 days.

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